

Study of Technical Tactical Actions of Professional Football Players during the Training Process

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Abstract:

The article provides information about the technique and tactics of skilled players.

Keywords: Football, tactical aspect, tactics, player, coach, training

INTRODUCTION

Football is the most popular and favorite game in most countries of the world. Hundreds of thousands of children, youth and adults play football. Management of the training process includes the study of various aspects of the special training of the players in order to organize the training in accordance with the individual characteristics of the players at the next stages. Football theory and practice are multifaceted and constantly developing. The relevance of the research lies in the fact that comprehensive information about the technical and tactical training of players who come to the coach using step-by-step, current and rapid management tools and methods is for the purposes of appropriate management, if the coach has only pedagogical skills. This means the ability to correctly use a wide arsenal of special exercises aimed at the superior development of some components of the players' special training; to rationally combine various exercises and methods of their implementation in accordance with the specific goals and tasks of training football players in various structures of the educational process.

The main problem is that, on the one hand, there is a need to improve international results and further development of football, and on the other hand, it is impossible to solve this problem without increasing the efficiency of training players, which should be based on the improvement of the sports reserve system for football in general. The primary form of gameplay should be team

combo play, not individual, although in some cases martial arts can be beneficial. The aggressive nature of the game undoubtedly gives an advantage, but in equal conditions, the victory will be won by the team that has mastered the art of maneuvering, and is better prepared technically and physically. Players must be motivated and motivated; they have to move for 90 minutes, they have to maneuver, they have to be very active all the time.

Football is the most popular and favorite game in most countries of the world. Hundreds of thousands of children, youth and adults play football, millions watch the game on TV. A large number of articles, news about competitions inform football fans about the status, development, prospects of the game, problematic issues, etc. The training of highly qualified players requires a lot of knowledge and high pedagogical skills from coaches. Science comes to the aid of coaches. In the near future, the creative cooperation of coaches with representatives of science will undoubtedly be one of the main sources of the rapid development of football and its qualitative development. One of the distinctive features of modern football is speed in the broadest sense of the word. Football has sped up. Now the athlete has to react quickly, think, act, implement technical techniques, quickly solve tactical tasks in various game situations. In this work, we will pay attention to the physical and technical training of the players. Taking into account the growing interest in football, it is recommended to consider this sport from different angles: game technique and tactics, influence on the development of motor skills, training for the game. It is known that the physical fitness of players is one of the most important factors that depends on the effectiveness of collective, group and individual technical and tactical actions. No matter how technically and tactically literate a football player is, he will never succeed without good and versatile physical training. A team whose physical fitness does not meet the standards of modern football will not be successful.

First, because in each game episode, several players solve a specific game problem at the same time. To do this, they need to perform coordinated actions in speed, space and game movements. And if at least one of them does not have a corresponding function, then it will not be possible to solve the problem of the game episode.

For example, a player with a weak physical condition will not have time to overtake the opponent in the fight for a tactically useful position, or lose the martial art for the ball, etc.

Secondly, because in the game, each player must quickly and accurately assess tactical situations, make clear decisions and immediately implement them. The tactical efficiency of players with insufficiently developed speed, response to a moving object (opponent, partner, ball) or selection speed is always low.

Third, football is becoming an increasingly popular sport, with active doubles and singles matches. Only an experienced player can win the fight for the ball, get rid of a dangerous collision and stand up after the opponent's push. Therefore, training with strong strength is an indispensable quality of a football player.

In the game, the player must perform many movements with maximum amplitude: kicks, kicks, kicks. They are only effective when the player has good flexibility. We also note that good flexibility is an indirect evidence that the player's muscles are flexible and in good condition. This condition of the muscles protects them from injuries. Therefore, good flexibility is an indispensable quality of a football player. Effective implementation of techniques is based on muscle and intra-muscular processes coordination or coordination ability. The ability of football players, especially young ones, to learn football techniques depends on them. No professional football player can be without well-developed coordination skills. All these qualities make up the players' physical fitness. Therefore, improving physical fitness is one of the most important tasks that football teams try to solve in training. Currently, the task of preparing a highly qualified reserve for professional football is being updated. The development trends of modern sports predetermine a long-term planned

process for achieving high skills, requiring the need to improve the system of its gradual formation. This is true for football. The training of athletes should be based on a consistent and consistent exercise methodology, which ensures the effective development of sports skills, the rapid growth of functional capabilities and their correct implementation, which is impossible without a carefully prepared initial stage of training.

CONCLUSION:

The main goal in the individual tactical training of the player is to develop the already existing tactical characteristics of the player, to develop new tactical methods based on individual characteristics, and to eliminate incorrect tactical skills.

In personal tactical training, it is important to develop the ability to choose a place or, as they say, to make a "plan". They are taught to "classify" as follows: 6-7 columns are placed in a limited area, approximately 10 X 10 m, without any system. The player moves with the ball and moves around these racks, facing this player on the other side. Once in a favorable position, the coach sends the ball to the floor to pass between several positions. The student is in constant motion, trying to find a path for the ball to travel, "classify" it and receive it. Gradually, the number of racks and the density of their location increases, as a result of which there are corridors where you can send the ball.

The following method is used to develop the goalkeeper's ability to seize the moment to run to the opponent in individual training. The player is required to move with the ball towards the goal; A goalkeeper is a must. pick a moment to grab the ball while running. This exercise is carried out after serious preparation of the goalkeeper and is carried out with maximum care.

In each such training, 20-30 "runs" are performed, initially the attacker should be slightly lower than the goalkeeper, this method quickly gives positive results.

Before personal tactical training, it is necessary to carefully choose methods that ensure the correction of shortcomings and instilling the necessary qualities in the players.

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